

BUILDING CAPACITIES IN INNOVATION PROCUREMENT FOR CITIES

D.2.2 Report on Market Consultation Activities

May 2023

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BUILD

Building Capacities in Innovation Procurement for Cities

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

BUILD	Building Capacities in Innovation Procurement for Cities
PPI	Public Procurement of Innovation

1 Introduction

The aim of this report is to provide insights on market consultation events for buyers and suppliers. The purpose of the workshops conducted within task 2.2 was to introduce the possibilities of public procurement of innovation (PPI) to the public sector and entrepreneurs and to identify barriers that cause the relatively modest share of PPI in public sector procurements. For entrepreneurs, in order to be interested in PPI or participate in them, it is an important prerequisite that PPI are announced. For this reason, four workshops were held, in which the barriers for the procurers as well as the suppliers in relation to PPIs were mapped. The possible solutions were also provided.

Table 1. Workshops and participants

Workshop	Target groups	Number of participants
03/03/2023 Turku	Procurers of City of Turku	9
09/03/2023 Turku	Public procurers in Finland	8
14/03/2023 Turku	Companies	15
21/03/2023 Tartu	Public procurers in Estonia	17
05/04/2023 Tartu	Companies	9

The procurers in Finland consist of procurement experts from universities, different municipalities, and procurement law experts from consulting companies. Participated companies represent following fields of industry: hardware, ICT, consulting, entrepreneur organizations and services such as maintenance.

In Estonia procurers that participated in the first workshop were mainly representatives of local municipalities, but also universities and some organisations. In the second workshop representatives from consulting companies, businesses, national organizations.

2 BUILD Market Consultation Activities

2.1 Methodology

Purpose of the workshops was to identify the barriers to conduct innovative procurement, and what could be solutions to overcome these barriers. Four on-line workshops were conducted, two in Tartu and two in Turku. Wide range of different stakeholders (representatives of local governments, universities, start-ups, SMEs, etc.) were invited. In each city, first workshops were dedicated to buyers and later ones to suppliers. In addition, Turku conducted one extra workshop for its own procurement specialists. MIRO board was used as a mapping tool. Turku had 4 facilitators in every workshop, Tartu had 3 facilitators in the first workshop and one in the second workshop. Results of the workshop were shared to all participants.

2.1.1 Topic/question:

What kind of barriers do we have in innovative procurements? What are the barriers/challenges and solutions?

2.1.2 Invitations:

Open invitation for companies (suppliers).

Invitations with the explanations about public procurement of innovation and about target of the workshops will be sent beforehand.

2.1.3 Workshops:

4 workshops with same structure but different audience:

- workshop for buyers in Tartu
- workshop for buyers in Turku
- workshop for suppliers in Tartu
- workshop for suppliers in Turku

Workshops length is maximum 2,5 hours, and they are held in the local language. In each workshop, 3-4 working groups are formed, which are moderated by the project partners who are organizing the workshop.

Workshop environments: Online workshops (if possible, then on site or hybrid), MIRO.

Participants (suggested 10-20 people):

- Buyers: Municipalities, universities, public owned companies, politicians.
- Suppliers: Companies (SMEs, start-ups) – different profiles, different sizes, politicians.

2.1.4 Structure:

1. Welcoming and Miro-board with the question: How much experience participants have? (10 min)
2. Introduction to the topic (What and why innovative procurement) and group dividing. (10 min)
3. Identifying barriers:
 - a. In small groups: Fill in as many ideas of barriers/challenges as they have in the MIRO (25 min)
 - b. In small groups: Choose 2 main points to present the others (5 min)
 - c. Back in big group: Present the 2 main barriers per group (15 min)

Break (15 min) meanwhile the moderators make a conclusion of the most mentioned barriers and chooses 3 barriers to fill in a new MIRO-board

4. Finding solutions to the 3 barriers:
 - a. In small groups: Fill in as many ideas of solutions to these 3 barriers. Consider the steps of the solutions and the key stakeholders. (25 min)
 - b. In small groups: choose one solution to each of the 3 barriers (5 min)
 - c. Back in big group: present the picked solutions. (25 min)
5. Conclusions and thanks (15 min)

2.1.5 Timeline

- Preparation – January
- Invitations - February
- Workshops – February, March, April

2.2 Communication

2.2.1 Tartu

In Tartu the participants were invited to the workshop by email (invitations can be found in Annex II). For the buyers' workshop, mostly the organizations involved in the Tartu Sustainable Living Lab were invited to participate (Tartu Sustainable Living Lab is established to bring together different organizations in order to find synergies to support the sustainable development of the region). Since we already have many cooperation partners there, it was rather easy to involve them. Colleagues from Tartu City Government were invited directly. First invitation was sent about a month before workshop and reminder about week before.

For the companies' workshop also some organizations from the Tartu Sustainable Living Lab were invited, but also different companies were mapped and invited via direct emails as well. First invitation was sent about a month before workshop and reminder about week before. Unfortunately, the interest and response from the companies was not as active as that of the suppliers.

After both workshops were conducted, all participants received a result. After both workshops PEDAL posted main findings to the LinkedIn page of the project.

2.2.2 Turku

First target group, Turku's own public specialists, was easy to approach as we are all working in the same team. The workshop event was scheduled in team members' calendars. The target group had had separate training about innovative procurement in theory in November 2022 so any other marketing or separate invitations with info weren't needed. For the other two workshops, a separate invitation (Annex III) was created.

For the second workshop, local public procurers were approached via email. As Turku cooperates with other municipalities and public procurers in the county of Southwest Finland, direct marketing was easy to conduct towards existing contacts. Valonia sent info about the event to its contacts via email. After sending the original email and one reminder afterwards, more enrollments were needed. Event was marketed to wider audience via LinkedIn and Turku's websites (figure 1).

With the third target group - companies, another marketing strategy was used. Local startups and SMEs were reached via different entrepreneur and startup associations. They were very cooperative and promised to share our invitation to their customers and connections. After weeks of waiting after their marketing efforts, it was decided to share the invitation to a wider audience. Third workshop was marketed via LinkedIn and Turku's website (figure 1) as well as in site hankintailmoitukset.fi. Hankintailmoitukset.fi is the official service for notices on public procurement in Finland. Public buyers publish notices on upcoming and ongoing tendering procedures and as well on the results of procedures.

All participants got an email after the workshop with screen prints of the outcomes. In addition, BUILD's and Turku's LinkedIn profiles were advertised as participants were guided to follow the profiles for later news and events. A post was created for PEDAL to post in BUILD's LinkedIn site.

Figure 1. LinkedIn post

2.3 Introduction to participants

In the EU, the purchasing power of public sector procurers is about 14% of GDP. In many European regions, public sector procurement plays an important role in the local economy. Public sector investments and innovation are two important ways to implement the green and digital revolution and create a sustainable economic environment. The main goal of public sector procurers is to achieve the most stable and reliable procurement result. They usually reduce risk by looking for established companies with an impeccable reputation and requiring standard solutions that have proven to be reliable.

Yet, public sector procurers can encourage innovation and offer important opportunities to companies, also SMEs and start-ups who may have solutions for different needs but have difficulties bringing them to market. Public sector procurers can give companies the opportunity to develop and test their solutions under real conditions. Despite their high purchasing power, public sector procurers still rarely carry out public procurements of innovation.

PPIs open the door to higher quality and more efficient solutions that value environmental and social benefits, greater cost efficiency and new business opportunities for entrepreneurs. Innovation can have different meanings and PPI is also often defined differently. In general, it can be said that PPI refers to any procurement in which either the process of innovation or the results of innovation are procured.

The purpose of the workshops conducted within the BUILD project is to introduce the possibilities of public procurement of innovation to the public sector and entrepreneurs and to identify barriers that cause the relatively modest share of PPI in public sector procurements. In cooperation with interest groups, we are looking for solutions to overcome these barriers and encourage a wider use of public procurements of innovation.

2.4 Tartu

2.4.1 Challenges and solutions from procurers' perspective

Challenges and their solutions from procurers' perspective presented in the table below.

Table 2. Challenges and their solutions from procurers' perspective in Estonia

Challenges	Details	Solutions
Lack of awareness	<p>What is PPI and how to recognize the element of innovation?</p> <p>It is often not thought that innovation partnership could be used in the procurement procedure.</p>	<p>Preparation of PPI materials (primary instructions, sample criteria).</p> <p>Availability and distribution of information in different networks (direct communication, raising the topic during meetings of existing networks).</p> <p>A constantly expanding list of already completed public procurements of innovation.</p> <p>Aim to make a certain number of PPIs in order to normalize this form of procurement.</p>
Complexity	<p>Innovation partnership has a complex methodology. In addition, the preparation of the initial task is difficult, specific competence and external help are necessary.</p> <p>Employees of municipalities lack the experience and skills to prepare and carry out the PPI.</p>	<p>Use of competence from outside. For example, the involvement of external consultants or other local governments in the designing of the procurement process.</p> <p>Sharing experiences and best practices.</p> <p>A list of successful PPIs to learn from (for example, information in the public procurement register).</p> <p>A cooperative group of local government procurement specialists who work together to gain experience.</p>

Finances	Lack of the available finances limits the use of PPIs. If trying something new doesn't work out, it's usually financially costly.	Support measures for carrying out PPIs.
Time	Public procurement of innovation takes more time (preparation and execution of the procurement).	Acknowledging that although the process is longer and more complicated at the beginning, the result is faster and better.
A safe approach	Instead of getting innovation, familiar and tested simple and safe solutions are used. PPI as a form is feared.	Various funding measures related to the green transition could include a requirement to use an innovation component. Similarly, to the criteria for green procurement, where specific product groups and services are specified, a similar legislation should be used for PPI.

2.4.2 Challenges and solutions from companies' perspective

Challenges and their solutions from suppliers' perspective presented in the table below.

Table 3. Challenges and their solutions from suppliers' perspective in Estonia

Challenges	Details	Solutions
Lack of competence	<p>Ignorance of how it would be better to organize an innovative procurement.</p> <p>Describing the expected results is complex.</p> <p>The procurement description tends to prescribe solutions.</p> <p>Underestimating the time and resources required for procurement preparation.</p> <p>There is no central competence center that would provide advice on various issues related to procurement (including technical issues).</p>	<p>National support structure with guidance materials.</p> <p>Involvement of experts and lawyers in the field in the preparatory phase (as well as during the execution of the procurement).</p> <p>Sharing success stories.</p> <p>More communication between local governments, but also with entrepreneurs.</p> <p>Suppliers can find solutions if given the chance. One could rely on what the market offers, but for that it is</p>

		necessary to leave an opportunity for that. It is important for an entrepreneur to have room to make mistakes.
Finances	Limited Resources	
Incomplete methodology	There is no good methodology for evaluating procurement results, even if we know what we want.	Tools that facilitate the evaluation of results (e.g., life cycle cost, etc.). Procurement procedures of public procurers should contain relevant provisions.
Time	Time consuming	To award participants, who took 2 nd and 3 rd places in public procurement of innovation. The method of recognition of PPS of the public sector.

2.5 Turku

2.5.1 Challenges and solutions from procurers' perspective

Challenges and their solutions from procurers' perspective presented in the table below.

Table 4. Challenges and their solutions from procurers' perspective in Finland

Challenges	Details	Solutions
Identification	How to identify public procurement of innovation? And who decides the definition and its meaning within the organization? Not only is it difficult to identify the innovation aspect, but also to identify the need and wanted results.	It is much more than procurement projects where innovation partnership is used . Procurement strategy and its targets might drive the findings of innovation aspects. Tool to identify innovation potential. Tools for identifying need and wanted results.

	<p>Innovations aren't encouraged during contract period.</p> <p>Lack of courage and certainty to call one's procurement as innovative.</p> <p>Attitudes are humble.</p>	<p>Buyers and end-users need to be strongly engaged in the market dialogue.</p> <p>Asking feedback of previous procurement projects and contracts, what could be improved for the next round?</p>
<p>Anticipation and timetable</p>	<p>How much time must be allocated compared to non-innovative procurement?</p> <p>How to anticipate the costs? Is it possible and to what extent?</p> <p>Often there is no time to do things differently because the deadline doesn't allow market dialogue, long procedures, and preparation time.</p> <p>How to get from reactivity to proactivity?</p>	<p>Description of the procurement needs must reach procurers in good time advance. Procurement plans must be at least annual. ☑ There should be a forum (procurement, management, finance) that makes the plan together.</p> <p>Buyers and management need to be educated about the importance of advance info.</p> <p>The innovation potential and chances need to be considered already in the budget so that there is flexibility if needed.</p>
<p>Involvement</p>	<p>Whole organization should be interested in improving procurements. Finding and creating innovations is not only a job of procurers. ☑ Often substance experts/buyers are not very interested in investing more resources in project.</p> <p>Management and finance need to be engaged and understand their impact in resources, risk management, timetables etc.</p> <p>How to convince the buyers of the new ways of operating? Attitudes towards change are challenging.</p> <p>How to get end-users involved?</p> <p>Companies should be involved more in the very early stages of planning a procurement.</p>	<p>Trainings to management, buyers, and procurers.</p> <p>Leading change with good explanations and fact-based data.</p> <p>Request for information is not enough. Procurers need to have an actual dialogue with companies where their point of view and ideas can be heard.</p> <p>There should be different methods of market dialogue in use. on-going dialogue in Miro? regular forums? Portal for sharing ideas and info of up-coming procurements?</p> <p>Co-creation of innovations should be encouraged and allowed during the contract period.</p>

<p>Market knowledge</p>	<p>The co-operation between markets and public procurers is little. All planning is done within the buyer organization.</p> <p>Are companies ready or willing to invest in our procurement with their ideas and time?</p> <p>Buyer has little knowledge about solutions that could be utilized. Therefore, it is easy to do, how it has been done previously.</p> <p>Companies are not telling their ideas proactively. What ways of market dialogue would lead to most open discussions?</p>	<p>Companies should have the information of up-coming procurement projects in good time advance. Tendering calendar.</p> <p>Following the markets during the contract period to be more aware of options when the next round comes.</p> <p>Companies could organize events where they share their new innovations for public buyers.</p> <p>More one-on-one dialogue between companies and procurers.</p>
<p>Lack of concrete instruction</p>	<p>How to consider innovation potential in every step of the procurement process? Where should I start?</p> <p>Which procurement procedure should I use to get the best result in each procurement?</p> <p>Concrete examples and criteria are needed.</p>	<p>Good, successful cases should be shared within organization. Channel for this is needed.</p> <p>Benchmarking.</p> <p>Guidelines for considering innovation aspects in every step of the procurement process from planning to contract period.</p>
<p>Know-how and comprehension</p>	<p>Lack of courage to try something new and fear of failure.</p> <p>The main goal and the whole term (IPP) are dusky. How to define IPP?</p> <p>Hard to delineate the procurement.</p> <p>Evaluation criteria are difficult to form.</p> <p>The idea that IPP is always more difficult and more expensive.</p>	<p>The goal is to procure the best possible result with the existing budget, not the innovativeness itself. That is also an easier message to promote.</p> <p>Trainings, knowledge sharing, motivating from listeners perspective.</p>
<p>Risk management</p>	<p>If the procurement need is crucial, are we ready to face risks of IPP?</p> <p>High risk of complaints that will prolong the process.</p>	<p>It is important to have enough substance experts involved.</p> <p>carrot and stick methods.</p> <p>Examples of risk sharing models.</p>

	<p>The flexibility of the budget when creating something new.</p> <p>How to divide risk between buyer and service provider?</p> <p>Are we able to perceive all crucial risks beforehand?</p>	
Resources	Lack of time, know-how, people, finance.	Engaging and training management of the topic.
Bureaucracy and law	<p>How can different innovative bids be evaluated even-handedly?</p> <p>How openly does the law allows us to do market dialogue?</p> <p>How can we buy the best alternative in the market when law states that multiple companies have to be able to bid?</p>	Trainings, example cases, guidelines what is ok and what's not.

2.5.2 Challenges and their results from companies' perspective

Challenges and their solutions from suppliers' perspective presented in the table below.

Table 5. Challenges and their solutions from companies' perspective in Finland

Challenges	Details	Solutions
Co-operation and trade secrets	<p>It is difficult to form a consortium to be able to bid to a larger entity. ☒</p> <p>Networking takes time and requires trust.</p> <p>Very little cooperation between buyer, procurer and company starting from planning the procurement till contract period.</p> <p>Market dialogue needs to be organized so that the dialogue is open and trade secrets are sheltered.</p>	<p>Rules and risk sharing need to be figured out in contract between consortium members.</p> <p>One-on one market dialogues and possibility for anonymous commenting are good procedures regarding trade secrets.</p> <p>Co-creation where all companies are in the same space, is difficult especially if it's organized in the later phases of the procurement process and not in the very start.</p>

<p>Involvement</p>	<p>Buyers are not involved in the procurement. They might decide not to proceed with the project.</p> <p>The content of the procurement is already decided. There is no chance to participate in the planning by coming up with different solutions to the problems and needs.</p> <p>Do buyers and procurers want to continue working with “old reliable partners” or to be open to new ones?</p> <p>Lack of pilots and daring on the procurer's side.</p>	<p>Companies should be informed and taken along already in the first steps of the process.</p> <p>There should be opportunities for discussion and affection in many phases during the procurement process.</p> <p>Substance experts need to be involved in every step of the process and especially to the market dialogue. Also, end-users and their wishes need to be heard.</p>
<p>Communication</p>	<p>Companies need a good description of the goals and needs of the buyer.</p> <p>Market dialogue could offer companies a chance to co-create solutions and ideas and form networks.</p> <p>Market dialogue is mostly insufficient. Instead of dialogue, the focus is on presenting the up-coming procurement.</p> <p>There should be more dialogue between companies and buyers.</p> <p>Procurement procedure process should be described to companies.</p>	<p>More innovative market dialogue with wider variety; There could be on-going portal where parties can discuss known problems, goals and needs and then a separate platform for sharing new ideas for buyers. These ideas could be awarded if they are proceeded.</p> <p>Procurers and buyers need to think what the goal of the market dialogue is. Presenting the procurement is not enough. How could they benefit out of those discussions? How companies really be for help?</p>
<p>Specification of a procured entity</p>	<p>Entities are too large. Buyer wants to have an overall package that one service provider produces. ☒ Innovative businesses that have specialized in one part of the process can't participate.</p> <p>The entity and its content have already been decided and often the wanted solution is the same old solution as before even if there would be new options lack of market survey and perhaps lack of substance experts.</p>	<p>Buyers and procurers need to consider if the entity could be divided into multiple sections.</p> <p>Instead of performing the same old same old, the entity should be focusing on the description of the problem, need and goals and trying to find the best solution.</p>

Comprehension	<p>Have we understood correctly buyer's needs? Especially without market dialogue.</p> <p>Different terms should be explained or written down clearly.</p> <p>The buyer doesn't see or even understand the innovation aspect in the procurement.</p>	<p>Market dialogue is important.</p> <p>Trainings to procurers and buyers.</p>
Delimiting award and comparison criteria	<p>Often award criteria is based on price and not on the quality factors.</p> <p>Many companies are limited from the tendering due to criteria regarding company size, references, and revenue.</p> <p>Innovation creation should be encouraged during the contract period, not only when the tendering is happening.</p> <p>Comparison criteria is often unclear. Compulsory criteria are often restrictive.</p>	<p>Procurers need to think, what criteria are crucial and what are there only for old habits or for unnecessary risk management.</p> <p>More opportunities to companies to take part in problem solving and to offer their ideas. Criteria should not limit this opportunity.</p> <p>Criteria should be more about the content and quality and clearly stated.</p>
Resources and timetable	<p>It takes time to prepare for a bid. Especially so if the company needs to form a network. Companies need info about up-coming procurements in advance. Bidding period should be reasonable.</p> <p>Is the contract profitable to us to bid? How much effort do we have to put into bidding?</p> <p>The first dialogues need to be organized in the very beginning of planning so that companies have possibility and time to impact on it.</p>	<p>There should be enough time in preparation for both sides, companies, and procurers.</p> <p>Do not ask for unnecessary documents just in case. Companies want to put their resources into discussions and documents that really create value to both sides.</p>
Risk management	<p>Who owns the end product that's created by co-creation?</p> <p>Who benefits the most? How can a win-win situation can be guaranteed?</p>	<p>Attractiveness should be increased.</p> <p>Examples of the risk sharing models are needed.</p> <p>Risk sharing should be discussed about in market dialogue.</p>

	<p>Initial investment is markable. What if the procurer interrupts the procedure or if we don't win the contract?</p>	<p>Check points for progressions and good monitoring of the contract.</p>
	<p>How to share the costs between buyer and company? How will the company be granted/rewarded?</p>	<p>Clarified roles.</p>

3 Summary

In all workshops, MIRO board was used for mapping barriers and proposing solutions (Figures 2 and 3). Along with the mapping, there was also intense discussion about the topic in the workshops. After mapping the barriers, two or three main barriers were identified, which were the most focused on in the search for solutions, but solutions were also offered to other barriers.

Figure 2. Filled MIRO board in Tartus' workshop

Figure 3. Filled MIRO board in Turku's workshop

In general, the number of PPIs in Estonia has been very modest. Public procurement of innovation is primarily associated with either innovation partnership or procurement of innovative and smart technical solutions. Most of the participants in Estonia have not had significant experience with PPIs.

Both, in Estonia and Finland it was pointed out, that it is difficult to identify innovative aspect in procurements, but also to describe the expected end result. Tools to identify innovation potential, experience sharing and dialogue with end-users are some of proposed solutions. Time and finances are also aspects that should be considered. Making long term procurement plans and taking IPs into account in the budget early on helps to manage these challenges.

Workshops showed that procurers lack knowledge and competence in the current field. Procurers also lack instructional materials, methodologies, helpful tools, and trainings, and need support in the form of specialist advice. It is necessary to develop support systems and make them as simple and accessible as possible. It encourages procuring innovation. It is recommended to introduce more widely the success stories, which increases the motivation of public sector procurers in procuring innovations.

Dialogue between procurers and companies should be on-going from the very start to the very end of the procurement process. To get innovative results, bilateral engagement and discussions are essential. The procurement description tends to prescribe solutions. Companies need good description of the goals and needs of buyer, but also room to develop these solutions. There should be enough time in preparation for both sides, companies, and procurers. Risk management should be considered. Different ownership rights, benefits, investments, etc., must be negotiated and different roles clarified.

Annex I: Tartu's invitations for participants

TARTU

KUTSE!

Innovatsioonihangete töötuppa

21.03.2023, kell 13.00-15.30

MS Teams keskkonnas

Avaliku sektori investeringud ja innovatsioon on kaks olulist viisi rohe- ja digipöörde elluviimiseks ning jätkusuutliku majanduskeskkonna loomiseks. Avaliku sektori hankijate peamine eesmärk on saavutada kõige stabiilsem ja usaldusväärsem hanketulemus. Tavaliselt vähendatakse riske, otsides juba turul kanda kinnitanud ettevõtjaid, kellel on laitmatu maine ning nõudes standardlahendusi, mis on osutunud töökindlateks. Sellegipoolest, avaliku sektori hankijad saavad soodustada innovatsiooni ning pakkuda olulisi võimalusi ka VKEdele ja idufirmadele, kellel võivad olla lahendused erinevate vajaduste jaoks, aga kellel on raskusi nende turule toomisega.

Innovatsioonihangetega avatakse võimalused kvaliteetsematele ja tõhusamatele lahendustele, milles väärtustatakse keskkonna- ja ühiskonnakasu. Innovatsioonil võib olla erinevaid tähendusi ja ka innovatsioonihankeid defineeritakse sageli erinevalt. Üldiselt võib öelda, et Innovatsioonihanked viitavad mis tahes hangetele, mille raames hangitakse kas innovatsiooni protsessi või innovatsiooni tulemusi.

Projekti BUILD raames läbiviidavate töötubade eesmärgiks on tutvustada innovatsioonihangete võimalusi ning tuvastada barjäärid, mis põhjustavad innovatsioonihangete senist küllalt tagasihoidlikku osakaalu avaliku sektori hangetes. Koostöös huvigruppidega otsime lahendusi, kuidas neid barjääre ületada ja soodustada innovatsioonihangete laialdasemat kasutamist.

Töötoas osalemine ei vaja eelnevat ettevalmistust.

Registreerumine kuni 16.03.2023: <https://forms.office.com/e/EW2XsFjEzZ>

Registreerunutele saadame lingi töötoa Teamsi keskkonda mõned päevad enne töötoa algust.

Kontakt:

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KUTSE!

Innovatsioonihangete töötuppa

05.04.2023, kell 13.00-15.30

MS Teams keskkonnas

Avaliku sektori investeringud ja innovatsioon on kaks olulist viisi rohe- ja digipöörde elluviimiseks ning jätkusuutliku majanduskeskkonna loomiseks. Avaliku sektori hankijate peamine eesmärk on saavutada kõige stabiilsem ja usaldusväärsem hanketulemus. Tavaliselt vähendatakse riske, otsides juba turul kanda kinnitanud ettevõtjaid, kellel on laitmatu maine ning nõudes standardlahendusi, mis on osutunud töökindlateks. Sellegipoolest, avaliku sektori hankijad saavad soodustada innovatsiooni ning pakkuda olulisi võimalusi ka VKEdele ja idufirmadele, kellel võivad olla lahendused erinevate vajaduste jaoks, aga kellel on raskusi nende turule toomisega.

Innovatsioonihangetega avatakse võimalused kvaliteetsematele ja tõhusamatele lahendustele, milles väärtustatakse keskkonna- ja ühiskonnakasu. Innovatsioonil võib olla erinevaid tähendusi ja ka innovatsioonihankeid defineeritakse sageli erinevalt. Üldiselt võib öelda, et Innovatsioonihanked viitavad mis tahes hangetele, mille raames hangitakse kas innovatsiooni protsessi või innovatsiooni tulemusi.

Projekti BUILD raames läbiviidavate töötubade eesmärgiks on tutvustada innovatsioonihangete võimalusi ning tuvastada barjäärid, mis põhjustavad innovatsioonihangete senist küllalt tagasihoidlikku osakaalu avaliku sektori hangetes. Koostöös huvigruppidega otsime lahendusi, kuidas neid barjääre ületada ja soodustada innovatsioonihangete laialdasemat kasutamist.

Töötoas osalemine ei vaja eelnevat ettevalmistust.

Registreerumine kuni 31.03.2023: <https://forms.office.com/e/KUrGSASBv0>

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Annex II: Turku's invitation for participants

Tahtotilana innovatiivisten hankintojen toteuttaminen? Niin meilläkin.

Tervetuloa Microsoft Teamsissa pidettävään innovatiivisten hankintojen työpajaan 9.3.2023 klo 9:00 - 11:30!

Työpajatyöskentely virittää osallistujat pohtimaan innovatiivisten hankintojen toteuttamisen ja niihin osallistumisen haasteita sekä näiden ratkaisuja. Työpaja on suunnattu Varsinais-Suomen alueella julkisia hankintoja tekeville.

Yhteiskunnan kannalta on tärkeää, että hankintoja tehdään innovatiivisesti jatkuvaa kehittymistä tavoitellen, mutta tästä huolimatta innovatiivisia hankintoja tehdään suhteellisen vähän. Työpajan tavoitteena on pohtia yhdessä, miten lisätä innovatiivisten hankintojen määrää julkisten hankintayksiköiden ja yritysten yhteistyönä? Mitkä asiat haastavat innovatiivisten hankintojen toteuttamista ja miten haasteita voitaisiin ratkaista?

Työpajatilaisuuden intro-osuuden jälkeen haasteita ja ratkaisuja ratkotaan yhdessä pienryhmätyöskentelynä. Työpajan kesto on 2,5 tuntia sisältäen vähintään yhden tauon. Osallistuminen ei edellytä mitään ennakko-osaamista tai valmistautumista.

Mikä innovatiivinen hankinta ja miksi?

Innovatiivisella hankinnalla tarkoitetaan uuden tai merkittävästi parannetun tuotteen tai palvelun hankintaa, jolla parannetaan julkisten palveluiden tuottavuutta, laatua, kestävyyttä ja/tai vaikuttavuutta. Innovatiivisuus voi liittyä hankinnan kohteeseen tai sen toteutusprosessiin.

Innovatiivisilla hankinnoilla voidaan saada aikaan sekä yhteiskunnallisia että taloudellisia vaikutuksia. Samalla voidaan aikaansaada taloudellisia vaikutuksia luomalla kysyntää yritysten uusille innovatiivisille ratkaisuille. Näin voidaan edistää yritysten innovaatio toimintaa ja liiketoiminnan kasvua sekä myönteistä työllisyys- ja talouskehitystä.

Varsin usein julkiset hankinnat toistavat vanhaa kaavaa. Käytännön taustalla on mm. riskien hallinta, jonka ohjaamana tilaaja tavoittelee stabiilia, jo riittävän hyväksi havaittua tapaa täyttää tarve. Käytäntö rajaa usein mahdollisuuksia lisäarvoa tuoville vaihtoehtoisille toteutuksille ja innovatiivisille ratkaisuille. Tästä syystä innovatiivisten hankintojen haasteet ja mahdolliset esteet on tärkeää hahmottaa ja pyrkiä aktiivisesti etsimään näihin ratkaisuja.

(Lähde & lisätietoa: [Valtioneuvoston julkaisu, Valovirta ym. 2017](#))

Ilmoittaudu mukaan!

Innovatiivisten hankintojen työpaja järjestetään etäyhteydellä Microsoft Teamsissa 9.3.2023 klo 9:00 - 11:30. Ilmoittaudu mukaan seuraavasta linkistä 6.3. mennessä:

<https://forms.office.com/e/N9zyvgL54h>

Saat linkin tilaisuuteen ilmoittautumisesi jälkeen.

Tervetuloa mukaan innovoimaan ratkaisuja yhdessä!

Työpajat pidetään osana BUILD-hanketta, jonka tavoitteena on innovaatiotiedon ja – taitojen kehittäminen yhdessä hankintayksiköiden ja tarjoajien kesken sekä innovatiivisten hankintojen määrän kasvattaminen Euroopassa. Tilaisuuden järjestää Turun kaupungin hankintapalvelut sekä kestävän kehityksen asiantuntijaorganisaatio Valonia.

Tiedustelut tilaisuudesta ja/tai BUILD-hankeesta voi osoittaa:

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